

A NEW SERIES OF SALTS OF HEXAFLUOROALUMINATE

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A new series of salts of hexafluoroaluminate group has been isolated. These compounds can be represented by the general formula: $M'M''AlF_6 \cdot 6H_2O$ (where $M' = NH_4, TP, Rb, K$, etc. and $M'' = Cu, Ni, Zn, Cd$, etc.). The corresponding sodium salts crystallise with four molecules of water. These sodium salts are also more soluble than the other salts. In chemical composition and in the order of solubility these compounds thus resemble the well known Schonite series. The compounds are perfectly stable under the ordinary laboratory conditions and they form very good crystals. Crystalline overgrowths have been observed in some cases. This fact suggests that like the Schonite series, the salts in this series also are isomorphous.

Aluminium gives rise to a few complex ions with fluorine. The whole series starting from $[AlF]^{2+}$ to $[AlF_6]^{3-}$ has been studied in solution Biosset, *Chem. Abs.*, 1943, 37, 138). In the solid state, however, only salts of $[AlF_4]^-$, $[AlF_5]^{2-}$ and $[AlF_6]^{3-}$ groups have been isolated. Of these ions, the $[AlF_6]^{3-}$ group, where aluminium is situated at the centres of regular octahedra with the corners shared, is the most symmetrical one (Brösset, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1937, 235, 139). The arrangement of the electrons is most suitable for d^2sp^3 hybridisation in $[AlF_6]^{3-}$ ion, but the $[AlF_6]^{3-}$ group in cryolite has been found to be somewhat distorted, and only strongly electropositive metals, such as the alkali and the alkaline earth metals, can afford salts with $[AlF_6]^{3-}$ ion. The pentafluoroaluminate ion, on the other hand, gives rise to salts with a good number of metals. No salts of the metals such as, Cu, Ni, Zr, etc., with the hexafluoroaluminate ion are known.

Attempts were made in this laboratory to isolate salts of hexafluoroaluminate ion with metals of the copper magnesium family. Each time a mixture of acid fluorides of the metals and the salts of the general type $M''AlF_6$ was obtained. A new series of compounds of the general type $M'M''AlF_6 \cdot 6H_2O$ (where $M' = K, NH_4, Rb, Cs, Tl^+$, but not Na^+ , and $M'' = Cu^{++}, Cd^{++}, Zn^{++}$ etc.) has, however, been isolated.

The corresponding sodium salts crystallised with four molecules of water. It may be mentioned in this connection that the Schonite series or Tutton's salts also behave similarly.

Wells ("Structural Inorganic Chemistry", Oxford Univ. Press, N.Y.) considers that the stable co-ordination number of aluminium with respect to fluorine is six. It is possibly due to some structural factors that no compound of the heavy metals with the hexafluoroaluminate ion was isolated previously. In the present paper the methods of preparation and properties of similar compounds with the general formula $M'M''AlF_6 \cdot xH_2O$ have been described.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fluorine was estimated as CaF_2 and also as $PbClF$. The metallic constituents were estimated after complete removal of the fluoride ion. The common methods were adopted for the determination of the percentage of the metals.

Methods of Preparation.—These compounds were prepared very easily. Requisite quantities of the three metallic carbonates, basic carbonates or the hydroxides were dissolved in hydrofluoric acid (about 10%), and heated to 80° in a platinum basin. A little excess of hydrofluoric acid sometimes helps the formation of these compounds. The solutions were then filtered, concentrated on a water-bath and allowed to crystallise in a vacuum desiccator. The insoluble alkali metal hexafluoroaluminates are usually precipitated down at first. The solutions were therefore filtered from time to time and the filtrates were allowed to crystallise. For the isolation of the sodium salts, the solutions were allowed to crystallise at a low temperature (10°). The preparation of the potassium salts was attended with maximum difficulties; addition of a few drops of amyl alcohol during the process of crystallisation was found to be more satisfactory.

Iron was easily converted into the ferric state in the presence of fluoride ion and so during the preparation of the iron compound, a few scraps of reduced iron were left in the solution. The following compounds were isolated :

Sodium copper hexafluoroaluminate tetrahydrate : (Found : Cu, 21.25 ; Al, 8.96 ; F, 37.68. $\text{NaCuAlF}_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 21.22 ; Al, 9.02 ; F, 38.05 per cent).

Potassium copper hexafluoroaluminate hexahydrate : (Found : Cu, 18.00 ; K, 11.01 ; Al, 7.58 ; F, 32.33 ; loss in wt. at 110°, 30.62. $\text{KCuAlF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 18.08 ; K, 11.11 ; Al, 7.66 ; F, 32.41 ; loss in wt., 30.73 per cent).

Ammonium copper hexafluoroaluminate hexahydrate : (Found : Cu, 19.20 ; Al, 7.99 ; NH_3 , 5.04 ; F, 34.38. $\text{NH}_4\text{CuAlF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 19.23 ; Al, 8.16 ; NH_3 , 5.15 ; F, 34.47 per cent).

Rubidium copper hexafluoroaluminate hexahydrate : (Found : Cu, 16.08 ; Al, 6.72 ; F, 28.53. $\text{RbCuAlF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 15.97 ; Al, 6.66 ; F, 28.63 per cent).

Potassium zinc hexafluoroaluminate hexahydrate : (Found : Zn, 18.42 ; Al, 7.6 ; F, 32.16. $\text{KZnAlF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Zn, 18.49 ; Al, 7.63 ; F, 32.24 per cent). Loss in wt. by the anhyd. salt at 120°, 30.66. (calc. loss in wt. for the anhydrous salt, 30.58).

Ammonium zinc hexafluoroaluminate hexahydrate : (Found : Zn, 19.23 ; Al, 8.32 ; NH_3 , 5.03 ; F, 33.98. $\text{NH}_4\text{ZnAlF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Zn, 19.61 ; Al, 8.39 ; NH_3 , 5.12 ; F, 34.29 per cent).

Potassium cadmium hexafluoroaluminate hexahydrate : (Found : Cd, 28.13 ; Al, 6.61 ; F, 28.17. $\text{KCdAlF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cd, 28.05 ; Al, 6.73 ; F, 28.47 per cent). Loss in wt. at 120°, 26.62 (calc. for the anhydrous compound, 26.99%).

Ammonium cadmium hexafluoroaluminate hexahydrate : (Found : Cd, 29.36 ; Al, 7.00 ; NH_3 , 4.41 ; F, 29.81. $\text{NH}_4\text{CdAlF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cd, 29.6f ; Al, 7.11 ; NH_3 , 4.49 ; F, 30.03 per cent).

Ammonium iron hexafluoroaluminate hexahydrate : (Found : Fe, 16.89 ; Al, 8.33 ; NH_3 , 5.20 ; F, 35.13. $\text{NH}_4\text{FeAlF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Fe, 17.29 ; Al, 8.54 ; NH_3 , 5.27 ; F, 35.29 per cent).

Ammonium cobalt hexafluoroaluminate hexahydrate : (Found : Co, 17.83 ; Al, 8.50 ; NH_3 , 5.13 ; F, 34.71. $\text{NH}_4\text{CoAlF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 18.02 ; Al, 8.55 ; NH_3 , 5.22 ; F, 34.96 per cent).

Sodium nickel hexafluoroaluminate tetrahydrate : (Found : Ni, 19.72 ; Al, 8.91 ; F, 38.42. $\text{NaNiAlF}_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 19.92 ; Al, 9.15 ; F, 38.68 per cent).

Potassium nickel hexafluoroaluminate hexahydrate: (Found: Ni, 16.83; K, 11.03; Al, 7.63; F, 32.69. $\text{KNiAlF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 16.92; K, 11.27; Al, 7.77; F, 32.86 per cent). Loss in wt. at 120° , 30.91 (calc. for anhydrous compound, 31.16%).

Ammonium nickel hexafluoroaluminate hexahydrate: (Found: Ni, 17.87; Al, 8.13; NH_3 , 5.38; F, 34.72. $\text{NH}_4\text{NiAlF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 18.01; Al, 8.28; NH_3 , 5.54; F, 34.99 per cent).

Thallium nickel hexafluoroaluminate hexahydrate: (Found: Tl, 39.38; Ni, 11.38; Al, 5.09; F, 22.20. $\text{TlNiAlF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Tl, 39.90; Ni, 11.46; Al, 5.27; F, 22.26 per cent).

General Properties.—The compounds isolated are crystalline and stable under normal conditions. On long exposure to the atmosphere the compounds slowly lose water and are converted into a white powdery mass. At high temperatures (above 80°) the compounds start losing water molecules. The substances left after heating the compounds to 100° are insoluble in water. This fact indicates that the compounds are converted into the fluoroaluminates of the alkali metals. The iron salt is most susceptible to decomposition in the presence of water vapour. Moist air easily turns this compound brown. The individual colour of the respective divalent metal ions are maintained in the compounds.

The sodium salts are highly soluble. The other compounds are also fairly soluble in water. Some of the insoluble alkali metal hexafluoroaluminates were precipitated at first when the compounds were redissolved in water. The precipitation is maximum in the case of the potassium salts.

Crystalline overgrowth has been observed in connection with a good number of salts (e.g. $\text{NH}_4\text{CuAlF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ on $\text{NH}_4\text{ZnAlF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{TlNiAlF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ on $\text{NH}_4\text{ZnAlF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$). This fact proves that like the alums and the Schonite salts, the whole series of compounds in this case are possibly isomorphous to one another.

The anomalous behaviour of sodium, apart from potassium and ammonium, has been observed in the case of the double salts before. This fact is once more recognised here. It is of interest to note that in the Tutton salts also, the corresponding sodium salts are most soluble and crystallise with four or two molecules of water.

The Cryolite is almost insoluble in water. The solubility of the sodium salt of this series suggests that in solution the ionisation possibly takes place as:

This complex anion then undergoes further dissociation as

Similar observations have been made in connection with the triple cyanides like $\text{M}'_2\text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, where it has been established that the cyanide groups are attached to both the iron atom as well as the other divalent atom (Keggin and Miles, *Nature*, 1936, 137, 577).

The author acknowledges his indebtedness to Prof. P. Ray, Director, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, for his kind interest during the progress of the work.